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European Neogene rodent communities: explaining family-level replacements through a spatiotemporal approach

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We analyse the changes in rodent regional assemblages based on 657 fossil-bearing western European localities distributed ranging from *ca.* 27 Ma (Late Oligocene) to *ca.* 3 Ma (Late Pliocene). We compare temporal and spatial patterns in order to identify the factors that drive the evolutions of communities. Regional assemblages are analysed based on the distribution of species richness among families. First, communities are temporally analysed to identify significant changes in their composition. Second, regional communities are spatially compared to identify diversity gradients. The temporal analysis reveals that communities' evolution is marked by several breaks in their composition, related to either migration or environmental/climatic events. This evolution can be summarised in terms of shifts in the relative abundances of glirids, cricetids and murids within assemblages. In contrast, spatial analysis shows that only environmental changes induce long-lasting changes in diversity gradients. Some observations made on cricetids and murids extant relatives indicate that they have undergone a large dietary diversification enabled by a specific digestive tract (along with the diversification of other life-history traits), whereas glirids are more specialised. The opposite diversity dynamics of these groups emphasises the importance of family-level adaptive potential in diversity conservation issues when facing environmental changes.

Keywords: Europe; Rodentia; life-history traits; family-level adaptive potential; Neogene; paleobiogeography

Introduction

The time interval between the Late Oligocene and the Late Pliocene is a period of transition in the evolutionary history of European mammals. Indeed, many dominant groups that had survived from the Paleogene were progressively replaced by new groups that are now important constituents of extant European mammalian faunas (Mein 1999a; Maridet and Costeur 2010). Therefore this time period is a key to understand how both biotic and abiotic factors have led to the construction of the mammalian diversity of the present day. The evolution of European mammalian paleodiversity and paleobiogeography is quite well known for this period, thanks to many synthetic studies (Fortelius et al. 1996; Geraads 1998; Costeur et al. 2004; Costeur and Legendre 2008b). These studies have generally pointed to a noticeable influence of climate on diversity as has also been observed for non-mammalian vertebrates (Ivanov et al. 2002; Böhme 2003). A recent quantitative paleogeographic study based on the distributions of various species of Glires (Maridet et al. 2007) demonstrated that the extant endemic pattern of small mammal distribution in Europe (Baquero and Tellería 2001; Krystufek and Griffiths 2002) is in fact rooted in a time long predating the first glacial cycles and mainly results from the successive climatic changes that occurred in the course of

the Neogene. This study emphasised that this period of time is critical for understanding the establishment of the extant diversity.

As far as community composition is concerned, extant European rodents are dominated by muroids (Herrera 1974; 77 species of rodents including 47 species of cricetids and murids). However, the diversity of these two families is not uniformly distributed among European communities. The existence of diversity gradients among rodents across Europe is known since decades (e.g. Herrera 1974; Letcher and Harvey 1994; Baquero and Tellería 2001), but latitudinal diversity gradients have also been recognised more specifically for arvicolines (Hanski and Henttonen 1996; Montuire et al. 1997) and murines (Aguilar et al. 1999). If on one hand the recent and fast diversification of cricetids and murids after their arrival in Europe in the Miocene has been extensively studied (e.g. Aguilar and Michaux 1996; Michaux et al. 1997; van der Meulen et al. 2005), the historical origin of the diversity gradients has, on the other hand, never been firmly established, nor investigated at broad spatial and temporal scales. At a scale close to the region, faunal assemblages result from species interactions such as competition and are functional groups reflecting resource partitioning in their ecosystems (Blondel 2003). Just as for metacommunities (Leibold et al.

2004), at this spatial resolution and on an evolutionary time scale, fossil rodent assemblages themselves react to both biotic (e.g. migrations) and abiotic (e.g. geographical and climatic parameters) factors. Both regional and provincial scales of analysis thus offer the possibility, using the fossil record, of investigating ecological processes that participate in establishing diversity gradients and shaping the compositions of communities (Escarguel and Legendre 2006; Escarguel et al. 2008).

Most previous studies focusing on the evolution of European Neogene communities were based either on specific or generic richness, using turnover rates or diversity/similarity indices to assess paleodiversity changes (e.g. Fortelius et al. 1996; Liow et al. 2008; Casanovas-Vilar et al. 2010), whereas the distribution of mammal species richness within families is also helpful in understanding evolutionary histories (Maridet and Costeur 2010). Indeed, as noted by several studies in the field of ecology (Ricklefs and Renner 1994, 2000; Qian and Ricklefs 2004), species richness alone is not sufficient for understanding the evolution of regional assemblages. Considering higher taxonomic levels can bring complementary and meaningful information. Indeed, the family level is known to provide reliable information on fine biogeographic patterns and evolutionary histories for both extant and fossil assemblages (Simpson 1964; Kaufman 1995).

Furthermore, factors rarely taken into account when attempting to explain community composition changes on evolutionary time scales are the ability of species or higher taxa to adapt based on their ecological requirements and to develop novel ecological features to face environmental change. Regarding this problem, the distribution of species richness within sister clades that compose a group (rodents in the present case) is a way to illustrate the complex branching structure of community phylogenies (Heard and Mooers 2000; Webb et al. 2002) and consequently the diversification of ecological requirements as a by-product of each taxon's history.

This study is based on an updated version of the data-set that was used for a previous biogeographic study (Maridet et al. 2007) and compares rodent communities through time, among the different European regions from the Late Oligocene to the Late Pliocene. The study presented here is a first attempt to temporally and spatially compare the family-level composition of Neogene European rodent communities (i.e. how species richness within a community is distributed among families and subfamilies) and to propose tentative hypotheses in order to further investigate long-term structuring and spatial differentiation processes within those communities, rather than to establish a definitive evolutionary history of European rodents. To do so, this study focuses on the evolution of rodent communities' composition at regional and provincial scales, and the historical origin of the diversity gradients along the Late Oligocene-to-Late Pliocene fossil record.

Materials and methods

Temporal and spatial setting

The ages of the localities used in this study range from *ca.* 27 Ma (million years ago; Late Oligocene) to 3.2 Ma (Late Pliocene). The temporal framework is based on continental biochronological units calibrated with dates from a recent geological time scale (Gradstein et al. 2004). Paleogene reference levels are used for the end of the Oligocene [reference levels Mammal Palaeogene (MP), MP28–MP30; Schmidt-Kittler et al. 1987; Biochrom'97 1997], and European Neogene Mammal Zones are used for the Miocene (biozones Mammal Neogene (MN), MN1–MN13; de Bruijn et al. 1992; Biochrom'97 1997; Mein 1999b) and up to the Pliocene (biozones MN14 and MN15; de Bruijn et al. 1992; Biochrom'97 1997; Mein 1999b). Biochronological units are defined at the European level on the basis of associations among some diagnostic mammal species with large geographical ranges. For each biochronological unit, a reference locality provides the typical association of evolutionary stages (chronospecies) observed in phyletic lineages. These associations allow the relative dating of other faunas. Thus, biochronological units are characterised at the continental level by faunal assemblages that are not significantly disrupted by origination, extinction or migration events, whereas such events are used to define the limits of these biochronological units. Consequently, each regional taxonomical assemblage defined in this study, for each biochronological unit, can reasonably be considered as a stable pool of species regionally coexisting throughout the corresponding time span. The calibration of biochronological units is based on magnetostratigraphic data from Steininger (1999) updated with the geological time scale calibration from Gradstein et al. (2004).

Several authors have discussed and questioned the accuracy of the European biochronologic framework for correlating the ages of localities across Europe (Fahlbusch 1991; de Bruijn et al. 1992; Steininger 1999; van Dam 2003; van der Meulen et al. 2011). These studies emphasise the fact that the first occurrences of some characteristic taxa are not synchronous in the different European regions, and may induce biochronologic correlation issues for localities of close age.

The broad temporal scale and the temporal interval considered here, including the Oligocene/Miocene and Miocene/Pliocene boundaries, were previously used as a characteristic time period to provide a synthetic view of small mammal evolutionary history. It enlightened diverse faunal changes that have been successfully correlated to world-wide climatic changes (Fahlbusch 1989; Maridet et al. 2007), thus demonstrating that uncertainties possibly due to the biochronologic framework induce no noticeable bias on long-term analysis of the fossil record. However, the potential impact of these uncertainties when compar-

ing the provincial communities' evolutionary patterns is discussed in detail below (see 'Biochronologic issues and broad spatiotemporal patterns' section).

The data-set used in this study includes localities covering Europe from the western Iberian peninsula to Greece (including Crete), via northern Europe. The former Yugoslavia was excluded from the database because this region contains too few localities, and the western part of the former Soviet Union was excluded because more work on standardisation of taxonomies needs to be done in this region in order to allow comparisons with the rest of Europe. All the regions considered in this study are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1, and a list of localities is given in the Supplementary online data (Text S1).

Data-set

A compilation of 657 localities that yielded rodents was undertaken and recently updated. Synonymies were corrected to make sure that any given species or lineage had the same name throughout the database. This work of systematic standardisation was made using published systematic revisions of small mammals (Mein and

Freudenthal 1971; Freudenthal et al. 1992; Daams and de Bruijn 1995; Rössner and Heissig 1999). When no such revision was available, the point of view of the original author(s) was followed. Then all of the localities from the same region (or sedimentary unit) and biochronological unit were grouped into a regional synthetic set.

Following the work of standardisation and compilation, it was necessary to select the regional data-sets in order to avoid biases such as insufficient sampling effort. Selecting data-sets based on the number of species alone would not be appropriate; sorting has consequently been undertaken on the basis of both specific and familial richness, adopting the rule that at least 10 species and 4 families should be represented in a regional list to be included in comparisons of community composition. This composition is illustrated by pie charts placed on the chronological scale and grouped by bioprovinces according to previously published results (Maridet et al. 2007). These comparison graphs have been produced for each of the 18 biochronological units spanning 24 My (from MP28 to MN15: *ca.* 27–3.2 Ma; Figure 2). A matrix showing the presence/absence of each fossil rodent species in each

Table 1. List of the 31 analysed regions, including the country, the province and any remarks about the regional fossil record.

No.	Country	Province	Region	Remarks
1	Portugal	Central Iberian	Tagus Basin	
2	Spain	South Iberian	Granada-Guadix-Baza	Only for the latest Miocene and Pliocene
3	Spain	Central Iberian	Madrid-Guadalajara	
4	Spain	Central Iberian	Duero	Insufficient fossil record, not used in this study
5	Spain	South Iberian	Jucar-Albacete	Only for the latest Miocene and Pliocene
6	Spain	South Iberian	Alicante-Murcia	Only for the latest Miocene and Pliocene
7	Spain	Central Iberian	Calatayud-Daroca-Teruel	
8	Spain	Central Iberian	Castellon-Valencia-Alcoy	
9	Spain	Peri-Pyrenean	Ebro and Bajo Ebro	
10	Spain	Peri-Pyrenean	Vallés-Penedés and Seu Urgell	Also includes the basins of Baix Empordà and Cerdanya
11	France	Peri-Pyrenean	Aquitanian Basin and Quercy	
12	France	Peri-Pyrenean	Languedoc-Roussillon	
13	France	Central French	Paris Basin	Until the Early Middle Miocene
14	France	Central French	Massif Central	Until the Early Middle Miocene
15	France	East French	Ardèche	Insufficient fossil record, not used in this study
16	France	East French	Provence	
17	France	East French	Centre-Est	
18	Switzerland	North Alpine	Swiss Molasse Basin	
19	Germany	North Alpine	RheinHessen	
20	Germany	North Alpine	Baden-Württemberg and Bayern	
21	Italy	Italian	Piedmont	Insufficient fossil record, not used in this study
22	Italy	Italian	Toscany	Only for biochronological unit MN13
23	Austria	Peri-Carpathian	Styrian and Vienna Basins	
24	Czech rep.	Peri-Carpathian	Bohemian Massif	
25	Slovakia	Peri-Carpathian	West Slovakia	
26	Hungary	Peri-Carpathian	Pannonian Basin	
27	Poland	Peri-Carpathian	South Poland	
28	Romania	South-eastern	North Dacic Basin	
29	Bulgaria	South-eastern	South Dacic Basin	Insufficient fossil record, not used in this study
30	Greece	South-eastern	Macedonia	
31	Greece	South-eastern	Central Greece and islands	

Note: For the numbers in the left column, refer to Figure 1.

Figure 1. Geographic location of the 657 localities and the 31 European regions used in this study, modified from Maridet et al. (2007). The list of localities used for this study is available in the Supplementary online data (Text S1). The numbers refer to the list of regions in Table 1.

combination of region and biochronological unit is given in the Supplementary online data (Table S1), which also includes the details of the number of species and number of families in each synthetic set (Table S2).

Classification of rodents

In this study, the classification used to describe rodent diversity is taken from Wilson and Reeder (2005). The Muroidea is a superfamily (Wilson and Reeder 2005) and includes the families Platacanthomyidae, Spalacidae, Cricetidae and Muridae. In this classification, Cricetinae and Arvicolinae are subfamilies of Cricetidae, and Murinae and Gerbillinae are subfamilies of Muridae. Nonetheless, the classification usually used in the Neogene fossil record presents some peculiarities that have to be taken into account. Thus the four subfamilies Murinae, Cricetinae, Arvicolinae and Gerbillinae are analysed here as equivalent to families, following common usage (Rössner and Heissig 1999). Even if Murinae, Cricetinae, Arvicolinae and Gerbillinae are not considered as families based on extant genetic features, the strong morphological differences among these groups as well as their abundance in the

Neogene fossil record imply very different ecological needs. When studying the distribution of fossil species richness among families as a mean of analysing the adaptation of rodent communities, these family-like features (morphological disparity, size disparity and species richness) justify the treatment of these subfamilies as family analogues in paleoecological studies.

Temporal analysis

Because the fossil record is not continuous, neighbouring regions presenting similar faunal assemblages have been grouped into provinces. Temporal evolution can then be compared across communities based on the familial species richness percentages for the five provinces presenting the longest fossil record. In order to describe and follow changes in their composition, biochronological units have been clustered based on the species richness per categories, using the program PAST (Hammer et al. 2001). This was done using an unweighted pair-group algorithm based on the average correlation between the proportions of any two given assemblages, used as a similarity measure between each pair of biochronological units. The clustering has been constrained by the chronological order of the biochronological units (allowing only adjacent units to be joined during the agglomerative clustering procedure). In addition to the clustering, the Mantel test has been used (based on 9999 permutations) in order to pinpoint significant similarities between each pair of successive community composition ($P \leq 0.05$).

Spatial analysis

The geographic distribution of species richness by family or subfamily was superimposed on paleogeographic European reconstructions (Rögl 1999; Solsona et al. 2000), for the different key periods identified from the temporal analysis within the time interval covered by our study (gerbillines are excluded because they are very weakly diversified and present during only two biochronological units). In order to reveal significant diversity gradients, correlations between species richness proportions and regional mean geographic coordinates were also calculated (Tables 2 and 3). As already stated (Rögl 1999; Meulenkamp and Sissingh 2003), changes in western European geography during the period covered by the study mainly consist of the disappearance of sea channels and the displacement of shorelines; mountain ranges having been well established and stable since the Late Oligocene. Consequently, geographic coordinates in western Europe have remained relatively unchanged since this time, and we therefore used extant coordinates to process the tests. Because of the low number of regions per biochronological unit, we chose to use the non-parametric Spearman's coefficient based on ranks (ρ). In addition, to make sure that patterns

observed are different from random, we use the same Mantel test (based on 9999 permutations) as for the temporal analysis, in order to test the significance of correlations ($P \leq 0.05$).

Results

Impact of sampling and parameters of analysis on taxonomic diversity

Before any analysis of the results, regional diversity (species and family richness) has to be tested for any potential bias that could affect its interpretation. Both the regional sampling effort (number of localities per region) and the potential influence of temporal and spatial scale have been tested. The surface area of each region was estimated based on the cartographic area of the sedimentary basin or geological formation used to define it (Figure 1; see Maridet et al. 2007 for area estimates). The durations of the biochronological units have been discussed by various authors (e.g. Agustí et al. 2001; Kálin and Kempf 2009; van der Meulen et al. 2011) and they have been shown to differ depending on the interpretation of the regional fossil records. In this study, the average durations of biozones at European scale are based on previously published estimates (Escarguel et al. 1997; Steininger 1999). For each pair of dependent–independent variables in the following observed correlations, the significance of the relationship is given by the non-parametric test of Mantel, based on 9999 permutations.

Figure 3 shows the relationships of both regional species and family richness with number of regions, biochronological unit duration and regional area, respectively. Three weak but significant relationships were observed: (1) between regional species richness and number of localities (Figure 3(a); $r^2 = 0.117$; Spearman $\rho = 0.353$; $P = 8 \times 10^{-4}$), (2) between regional family richness and biochronological unit duration (Figure 3(e); $r^2 = 0.098$; Spearman $\rho = -0.284$; $P = 6 \times 10^{-4}$) and (3) between regional family richness and region's area (Figure 3(f); $r^2 = 0.053$; Spearman $\rho = 0.194$, $P = 0.015$).

However, this study does not independently analyse the species and family richness in communities, but rather the distribution of species richness within families. Pielou's index, a classical index used to quantify diversity evenness in ecological studies (Beisel et al. 2003), was calculated based on familial species richness (including muroid subfamilies) in order to assess the potential impact of these biases on the composition of the observed regional assemblages. As for taxonomic richness, both the number of regional localities and the biochronological unit duration show a significant impact on estimated diversity (Figure 4(a): $r^2 = 0.058$; Spearman $\rho = -0.209$; $P = 0.012$; Figure 4(b): $r^2 = 0.090$; Spearman $\rho = -0.312$; $P = 1.3 \times 10^{-3}$). However, in both cases the percentage of paleodiversity explained by data

construction artefacts is low, the higher correlation observed (between biochronological unit duration and Pielou's index) being only around 9%. It is notable that this result may be partly influenced by rare and poorly diversified families, whose species are more likely to be found if sampling effort is intense. Accordingly, as this study focuses mainly on the principal (most abundant and diversified) families and subfamilies constituting the communities, it is necessary to test whether different categories illustrated in the pie charts (Figure 2) are truly affected by sampling effort (the number of localities used to build each pie chart). The result for each category is given in Figure 5. Species richness is not significantly biased by sampling effort for 'Murinae' and 'other families' (Figure 5(a),(c),(f)). The 'Arvicolinae' and 'Gerbillinae' seem also not to show significant bias, but the low number of points does not allow drawing a firm conclusion (Figure 5(d),(e)). Finally, the 'Gliridae' and 'Cricetinae' (Figure 5(a),(b)) are the only categories which are clearly significantly biased ($P = 0.032$ and 0.021 , respectively), but even here the coefficient of correlation shows that <6% of familial species richness is explained by sampling effort. Based on these results, the family-level composition used to temporally and spatially analyse the evolution of communities is weakly influenced by the potential biases previously tested. The distribution of species richness across communities as illustrated in the pie diagrams (Figure 2) hence reflects a very-close-to-real family-level composition of the faunas at the regional scale. It is hence possible to further interpret the evolution of communities in order to identify the main factors that may determine the evolutionary trends involved.

Temporal evolution of communities

The chronological evolution of rodent communities has been analysed for five provinces, which have sufficiently long and overlapping fossil records to allow the identification of common significant changes through time (Figures 6 and 7).

All the provinces with a fossil record starting in the Oligocene show a first change in their faunal composition between the Late Oligocene and the Early Miocene (MP 30–MN 1, ca. 23.0 Ma) as indicated by the clustering. However, the positive results of the Mantel test indicate that these changes are rather progressive and do not constitute a sudden break in communities' composition. This progressive change includes the disappearance of Theridomyidae at the Oligocene–Miocene boundary, although this clade had a substantial presence in the analysed communities during the Oligocene (see 'other families', Figure 8). So far only the occurrence of a short and intense worldwide glaciation event at the Oligocene–Miocene boundary (Naish et al. 2001), also recognised in the terrestrial fossil record of Europe (Mosbrugger et al. 2005), seems to be coeval with

Figure 2. Pie diagrams of regional rodent communities for each European region from the Late Oligocene to the Late Pliocene. The pie charts illustrate the number of species within families and murid subfamilies, focusing on glirids (black), cricetids (dark grey) and murids (light grey). Inside cricetids and murids, arvicolines are indicated by horizontal hatching and gerbillines by vertical hatching respectively. Other families have been grouped in this graphical representation (white) for easier reading. The family-level composition of each community is given for successive biochronological units, according to the MP and MN biochronological scales (see 'Materials and Methods' section for details). The calibration of biochronological units is based on magnetostratigraphic data from Steininger (1999) updated with the geological time scale calibration from Gradstein et al. (2004). For the numbers of the regions, refer to Table 1 and Figure 1.

Figure 3. For each region in each biochronological unit. (a–c) Log–log relationships between the regional species richness (dependent variable) and (a) the number of localities ($r^2 = 0.117$; Spearman $\rho = 0.353$; $P = 8 \times 10^{-4}$), (b) the time duration of each biochronological unit ($r^2 = 0.007$; Spearman $\rho = 0.058$; $P = 0.380$) and (c) the region’s area ($r^2 = 0.001$; Spearman $\rho = 0.059$; $P = 0.728$). (d–f) Log–log relationships between the regional family richness (dependent variable) and (d) the number of localities ($r^2 = 2 \times 10^{-5}$; Spearman $\rho = 0.032$; $P = 0.959$), (e) the time duration of each biochronological unit ($r^2 = 0.098$; Spearman $\rho = -0.284$; $P = 6 \times 10^{-4}$) and (f) the region’s area ($r^2 = 0.053$; Spearman $\rho = 0.194$, $P = 0.015$). Biochronological unit duration values are in millions of years, as estimated from Escarguel et al. (1997) and Steininger (1999), and regional area values are in km^2 and are taken from Maridet et al. (2007). The significance of the relationship (P) is given by the non-parametric test of Mantel, based on 9999 permutations.

Figure 4. For each region in each biochronological unit, relationships between the Pielou index calculated on distribution of species richness within families (dependent variable) and (a) the Log of the number of localities ($r^2 = 0.058$; Spearman $\rho = -0.209$; $P = 0.012$), (b) the Log of the time duration of each biochronological unit ($r^2 = 0.090$; Spearman $\rho = -0.312$; $P = 1.3 \times 10^{-3}$). The biochronological units duration values are in millions of years estimated from Escarguel et al. (1997) and Steininger (1999), and regional area values are in km^2 taken from Maridet et al. (2007). The significance of the relationship (P) is given by the non-parametric test of Mantel, based on 9999 permutations.

Figure 5. For each category illustrated in the pie charts in Figure 2, relationships between the Log of species richness (dependent variable) and the Log of the number of localities, n being the number of pie charts where the category is present. The different categories are (a) the family Gliridae ($n = 107$; Spearman $\rho = 0.224$; $r^2 = 0.039$; $P = 0.043$), (b) the subfamily Cricetinae ($n = 107$; Spearman $\rho = 0.227$; $r^2 = 0.055$; $P = 0.027$), (c) the subfamily Murinae ($n = 36$; Spearman $\rho = 0.258$; $r^2 = 0.050$; $P = 0.189$), (d) the subfamily Arvicolinae ($n = 14$; Spearman $\rho = -0.384$; $r^2 = 0.164$; $P = 0.150$), (e) the subfamily Gerbillinae ($n = 6$; Spearman $\rho = 0.000$; $r^2 = 0.003$; $P = 0.802$) and (f) the ‘other families’ ($n = 105$; Spearman $\rho = 0.012$; $r^2 = 0.005$; $P = 0.492$). The significance of the relationship (P) is given by the non-parametric test of Mantel, based on 9999 permutations.

the observed changes; however, a link between this climatic event and the change in community composition is difficult to establish.

The second change occurs during the late Early Miocene, between MN3 and MN5 (*ca.* 17.8–16.7 Ma) in the southern provinces (Figure 6) and at the end of the Early Miocene, between MN5 and MN6 (*ca.* 15.0 Ma) in the other

provinces based on the clustering (Figure 7). Furthermore, the results of the Mantel test indicate that the changes occurring from MN3 to MN6 in the Peri-Pyrenean province are rather fast compared to other provinces. A first significant break in communities’ composition indicated by both the Mantel test and the clustering occurs between MN5 and MN6 in north Alpine. This first break occurs

Figure 6. Distribution of species richness among gliroids, cricetids (cricetines and arvicolines) and murids (murines and gerbillines) plus other families grouped together (see Figure 2 for a presentation of the categories), for 'C. Iberian' and 'Peri-Pyrenean' provinces. The regions composing these provinces are presented in Table 1 and Figure 2 and are based on previous biogeographic analysis (Maridet et al. 2007). Adjacent biochronological units are clustered based on the average correlation between the proportions of any two given assemblages, used as a similarity measure between each pair of biochronological units. The result of the Mantel test (based on 9999 permutations) between each pair of successive community composition is given in the right side of the figure (* $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$).

Figure 7. Distribution of species richness among glirids, cricetids (cricetines and arvicolines) and murids (murines and gerbillines) plus other families grouped together (see Figure 2 for a presentation of the categories), for ‘E. France’, ‘north Alpine’ and ‘Peri-Carpathian’ provinces. The regions composing these provinces are presented in Table 1 and Figure 2 and are based on previous biogeographic analysis (Maridet et al. 2007). Adjacent biochronological units are clustered based on the average correlation between the proportions of any two given assemblages, used as a similarity measure between each pair of biochronological units. The result of the Mantel test (based on 9999 permutations) between each pair of successive community composition is given in the right side of the figure (* $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$).

Figure 8. Details of family-level composition discussed in the text, for three biochronological units: MP28, Late Oligocene; MN4, late Early Miocene; MN13, Latest Miocene; MN15, Late Pliocene. For each family or subfamily, the number of species is given on the pie charts. For the numbers of the regions, refer to Figure 1 and Table 1.

during the well-documented late Early Miocene–early Middle Miocene ‘climatic optimum’ (ca. 17–14 Ma; Wright and Miller 1992; Böhme 2003; Costeur and Legendre 2008a). This period is indeed known as a period of relative climatic stability on the European scale but follows a migration event: (1) the continued anticlockwise rotation of the African Plate led to a contact, known as the ‘*Gomphotherium* land bridge’, between the Arabic and Anatolian plates on one side and the Balkans on the other side (Rögl 1999). This new terrestrial domain enabled the arrival in Europe of numerous mammalian species from Asia and Africa, especially new cricetines originated from Asia (MN4; Mein 2003; Maridet et al. 2011). Among cricetine rodents, this period is characterised by Oligocene-inherited cricetines being rapidly replaced by newly arrived cricetines. This important turnover is well known as it has been described and discussed by many authors (e.g. Huguency 1999; Kälin 1999; Mein 1999a; Casanovas-Vilar et al. 2010; Maridet and Costeur 2010); however, our results show that this drastic renewal at generic and specific levels induces a quite progressive change at familial level. (2) The arrival in Europe of new rodent genera (*Albanensia* Mein,

1970; *Forsythia* Mein, 1970) but also likely immigrant lineages of already settled genera (Maridet and Sen 2012) attests to the persistence of migration events until the beginning of MN6 (ca. 15.0 Ma), even though they seem less important than the previous ones based on the number of species involved (Fortelius et al. 1996).

The next major change occurs during the early Late Miocene, between MN9 and MN10 (ca. 9.7 Ma). It is, however, not significant based on the results of the Mantel test for the Peri-Carpathian province. The main migration event occurring at the beginning of the Late Miocene is the arrival of the first true murines (MN9, ca. 11.1–9.7 Ma). Interestingly, this event does not significantly affect all the assemblages (only four MN9 localities in our database yielded murine specimens: Priay B, Castelnou 1B, Pedregueras 2C and Can Llobateres 1). Instead, the next break in their composition occurs later, between MN9 and MN10 (ca. 9.7 Ma). This is roughly coeval with the so-called Vallesian Crisis, showing the replacement of forest-dominated environments by more open landscapes in western Europe (Agustí and Moyà-Solà 1990). The first observed occurrences of murines in Turkey at about

Table 2. Correlations between the proportion of species per family (same categories as in Figure 2) and the mean geographic coordinates of each region, for the reference levels and biochronological units MP28 to MN15, except for MN2b and MN12 of which the number of regions was insufficient.

		Proportion of species vs. latitude				Proportion of species vs. longitude			
		Gliridae	Cricetidae	Muridae	Other	Gliridae	Cricetidae	Muridae	Other
MN15	ρ	0.177	0.353	– 0.886	0.603	–0.084	0.057	– 0.859	0.766
$N = 8$	P	0.697	0.405	0.003	0.123	0.836	0.903	0.026	0.030
MN14	ρ	0.714	0.167	– 0.805	0.833	0.381	0.071	– 0.463	0.786
$N = 8$	P	0.030	0.843	0.001	0.011	0.410	0.665	0.049	0.021
MN13	ρ	0.683	–0.467	–0.524	0.347	0.275	– 0.790	–0.214	0.539
$N = 8$	P	0.009	0.150	0.395	0.897	0.671	0.016	0.349	0.053
MN11	ρ	0.500	– 0.790	– 0.900	0.800	0.900	–0.335	–0.600	0.300
$N = 5$	P	0.391	0.020	0.037	0.104	0.037	0.417	0.285	0.624
MN10	ρ	0.167	– 0.870	–0.186	0.259	0.385	–0.544	–0.458	0.059
$N = 9$	P	0.667	0.002	0.631	0.500	0.306	0.130	0.215	0.881
MN9	ρ	0.609	–0.714	–0.698	0.257	0.551	– 0.943	–0.880	0.714
$N = 6$	P	0.173	0.056	0.168	0.309	0.595	0.039	0.066	0.095
MN7/8	ρ	–0.464	–0.048	–	0.321	– 0.464	–0.134	–	0.321
$N = 7$	P	0.056	0.928	–	0.245	0.041	0.770	–	0.127
MN6	ρ	–0.600	–0.200	–	0.600	–0.300	0.000	–	0.200
$N = 5$	P	0.406	0.827	–	0.247	0.689	0.924	–	0.716
MN5	ρ	–0.024	–0.286	–	0.214	0.214	–0.524	–	–0.071
$N = 8$	P	0.800	0.461	–	0.090	0.296	0.139	–	0.934
MN4	ρ	–0.372	0.146	–	0.191	– 0.700	–0.146	–	0.836
$N = 11$	P	0.381	0.940	–	0.374	0.002	0.650	–	> 0.001
MN3	ρ	– 0.865	0.464	–	0.928	–0.612	0.143	–	0.786
$N = 7$	P	0.006	0.182	–	0.027	0.191	0.876	–	0.023
MN2a	ρ	–0.435	0.116	–	0.029	–0.319	0.348	–	–0.029
$N = 6$	P	0.389	0.827	–	0.957	0.538	0.499	–	0.957
MN1	ρ	–0.314	0.314	–	0.058	–0.257	0.548	–	0.040
$N = 6$	P	0.544	0.544	–	0.913	0.623	0.260	–	0.940
MP30	ρ	0.200	0.257	–	–0.373	0.257	0.029	–	–0.530
$N = 6$	P	0.704	0.623	–	0.466	0.623	0.957	–	0.280
MP29	ρ	0.116	0.319	–	–0.143	0.116	0.319	–	–0.143
$N = 6$	P	0.827	0.538	–	0.787	0.827	0.538	–	0.787
MP28	ρ	–0.359	–0.300	–	0.200	–0.359	–0.300	–	0.200
$N = 5$	P	0.553	0.624	–	0.747	0.553	0.624	–	0.747

Notes: N represents number of regions; ρ , Spearman's rank correlation coefficient; P , Mantel test of significance based on 9999 permutations. Significant correlations ($P \leq 0.05$) are indicated in bold characters.

Table 3. Correlations between the proportion of species per subfamily (same categories as in Figure 2) and the mean geographic coordinates of regions, for each biochronological unit illustrated in Figure 10.

		Proportion of species vs. latitude				Proportion of species vs. longitude			
		Cricetinae	Arvicolinae	Murinae	Gerbillinae	Cricetinae	Arvicolinae	Murinae	Gerbillinae
MN15	ρ	–0.371	0.592	– 0.886	–	–0.698	0.590	– 0.859	–
$N = 8$	P	0.369	0.127	0.003	–	0.054	0.125	0.026	–
MN14	ρ	0.000	0.179	– 0.639	0.382	0.214	0.460	– 0.687	0.246
$N = 8$	P	0.980	0.707	0.013	0.351	0.638	0.100	0.023	0.329
MN13	ρ	–0.503	0.247	–0.144	–0.545	– 0.826	0.082	–0.239	–0.109
$N = 8$	P	0.096	0.486	0.782	–0.166	– 0.030	0.867	0.416	0.979
MN11	ρ	0.103	0.354	– 0.900	–	0.205	0.707	0.600	–
$N = 5$	P	0.897	0.406	0.025	–	0.317	> 0.001	0.157	–

Notes: N represents number of regions; ρ , Spearman's rank correlation coefficient; P , Mantel test of significance based on 9999 permutations. Significant correlations ($P \leq 0.05$) are indicated in bold characters.

Figure 9. Proportional species richness values (in percentages) for particular categories (glirids, cricetids and ‘other families’) in particular regions, superimposed on paleogeographic reconstructions of Europe (Rögl 1999; Solsona et al. 2000) for different key periods (provided by the temporal analysis) from the Late Oligocene to the Late Pliocene.

10.3 Ma (Sen et al. 1986) and in western Europe at 9.7 Ma (van Dam et al. 2001) contradict the pattern observed in our results, suggesting either that the biochronologic age of several murine-bearing localities included in our database, or the age estimation of the MN9 limits, might be biased. The significant break in rodents’ composition observed later, between MN9 and MN10 (*ca.* 9.7 Ma), might reflect the actual main dispersion event of the family across Europe, keeping in mind that this event likely was a gradual process (Michaux et al. 1997).

Except for the north Alpine province of which analysed fossil record stops in MN11, all other provinces show a last break in their faunal composition between MN11 and MN13 (before or after MN12, *ca.* 7.8–6.8 Ma, depending on the province). This break is supported by both the results

of the clustering and the Mantel test except for the Peri-Carpathian province. At the same time, the other families (Hystricidae, Dipodidae and Eomyidae) decline in diversity (Figures 2 and 8). Furthermore, the ‘Messinian event’, an environmental change affecting mainly the peri-Mediterranean area, occurs at the end of this period (during the biozone MN13). During this time interval, repeated interruptions in the Atlantic–Mediterranean connection, due to falling sea levels and tectonic activity in the Betic and Rifian corridors, led to a Mediterranean drawdown (Hsü et al. 1973; Clauzon et al. 1996; Meulenkamp and Sissingh 2003). As a consequence of this perturbation, land connections were established, and faunal exchanges occurred between the European and African continents (van der Made 1999; Agustí, Garcés et al. 2006). This last

Miocene event seems to cause a break in community composition between MN12 and MN13 (*ca.* 6.8 Ma), but surprisingly not between MN13 and MN14 (Costeur et al. 2007), lending credence to scenarios of early faunal exchanges between Europe and North Africa owing to the formation of land bridges, due to intensive tectonic activities in the Late Miocene of southern Europe (e.g. Azzaroli and Guazzone 1979; Sartori 2001; Krijgsman et al. 2002; Rook et al. 2006; Abbazzi et al. 2008). Although the arrival of the first gerbillines in the southernmost regions (Figure 8) was obviously made possible by these land connections at the end of the Miocene, it is noteworthy that the temporal and geographical distribution of the subfamily remains limited and that climatic factors, such as the maximum levels of aridity occurring at the same time in Europe (Blanc 2000), might also have constrained their arrival in Europe.

Except in the Peri-Carpathian assemblage (Figure 7), which shows a drastic increase in arvicoline diversity at MN15 (*ca.* 4.0 Ma), no break occurs between MN14 and MN15 (*ca.* 5.2–3.2 Ma), indicating that the hierarchical composition of the communities that would later face the Quaternary glaciations was already settled by the end of the Miocene.

Spatial differentiation among communities

The temporal analysis provided us with the key transitional periods in the evolutionary history of European rodent communities. During the last 25 Ma, European geography has changed drastically, leading to the extant coastlines and mountain ranges. We can evaluate the impact of geography on the differentiation of regional assemblages as Figure 8 shows the detailed composition of selected communities for some key periods of time, and Figures 9 and 10 show how the proportional species richness of each main family or subfamily varied through time in particular parts of the changing paleogeographic map of Europe.

From the Late Oligocene to the beginning of the Miocene, no significant heterogeneous spatial pattern prevails, and community composition is highly similar across Europe. The first significant pattern appears at the end of the Aquitanian (MN3, *ca.* 20 Ma) with two significant and opposed latitudinal gradients for glirids and the category ‘other families’ and also a significant longitudinal gradient for ‘other families’. At the same time the cricetid is poorly diversified in regional communities and shows no significant gradient, illustrating their fading which eventually led to the so-called ‘Cricetid Vacuum’ (Kålin 1999). This mostly latitudinal pattern for glirids and ‘other families’ turns into a longitudinal pattern at the end of the Early Miocene (MN4, *ca.* 17.8 Ma), a time when glirids, and to a lesser extent cricetines, diversify rapidly to the detriment of other families: the diversity of our category ‘other families’ decreases along a westward gradient,

whereas Gliridae show an opposite gradient (Figure 9), resulting in a significant correlation between longitude and proportion of species for both categories (Table 2). Otherwise, the central Iberian assemblages (Catalayud-Daroca-Teruel and Tagus basin) show a family richness lower than in other provinces (MN4: *ca.* 17.8–16.7 Ma; Figure 8), but are nevertheless mainly composed of cricetine and glirid species. To the north, on the other side of the Rhine Graben sea channel, regions within the north Alpine and Peri-Carpathian provinces present quite different proportions of glirids and cricetines (Figure 9), but also differ from the southern provinces in detailed community composition (Figure 8), in that anomalomyids are present and species richness is generally lower. The family Platacanthomyidae is also present in these three regional assemblages, whereas it is absent in the other regions. The Greek assemblage is distinguished by the presence of the family Spalacidae, and the presence of the family Anomalomyidae also confirms the assemblage’s more eastern overall affinities (MN4: *ca.* 17.8–16.7 Ma; Figure 8) as already demonstrated (Maridet et al. 2007).

However, this pattern immediately disappears at the end of the Early Miocene and during the Middle Miocene, and is replaced by a new homogeneous distribution of family diversity patterns across Europe, except of the significant longitudinal gradient for glirids in MN7/8. The next significant gradient appears at the beginning of the Late Miocene (MN9, *ca.* 11.1 Ma, Figures 9 and 10). A significant diversity gradient involving cricetids occurs from west to east (Table 2). The first murines are restricted to the south-eastern regions. This illustrates their progressive colonisation of Europe (Michaux et al. 1997).

During the Late Miocene, the increasing diversity of murines occurs mainly at the expense of glirids except in the Styrian and Vienna basins, in which glirid diversity seems to be maintained for a longer period. Later, the first arvicolines are recorded in Europe (MN11, *ca.* 8.8 Ma), but their geographic distribution is at first very limited (Figure 10). At the same time, two significant gradients appear: a significant north–south gradient for Muridae (which will maintain later through the Pliocene) and an east–west gradient for Gliridae. Among other families, eomyids are no longer present in Iberian faunas whereas they are still present in other regions (Figure 8). This emphasises the strong faunal differentiation that occurs between regional communities, as already observed based on species distributions (Maridet et al. 2007).

The very end of the Miocene Epoch (MN13, *ca.* 6.8–4.9 Ma) shows a change in the gradients: Gliridae are now significantly more diversified in northern regions, whereas ‘other families’ seem more diversified in eastern regions. The composition of ‘other families’ differs indeed significantly from one region to another (Figure 8), the Iberian Peninsula localities especially differ from the rest of Europe in not having Anomalomyidae, Spalacidae, Eomyidae and

Figure 10. Proportional species richness values (in percentages) for murines, cricetines and arvicolines in particular regions, superimposed to paleogeographic maps (Rögl 1999; Solsona et al. 2000) for different key periods (provided by the temporal analysis) from the Late Miocene to the Late Pliocene (except for gerbillines which are very weakly diversified and present during only two biochronological units).

Dipodidae in their assemblages (at the exception of a dipodid discovered in the northernmost Cerdanya basin in Spain; Agustí, Oms et al. 2006). This differentiation, however, does not lead to a significant longitudinal gradient for ‘other families’ in MN13 (Table 2). The Iberian Peninsula is also differentiated from the rest of Europe by higher proportions of cricetines and murines, despite the fact that the gradients are not significant for murines (Table 3 and Figure 10). This slight break in the establishment of diversity gradients might be the result of faunal exchanges between the European and African continents due to the Messinian event. However, significant diversity gradients reappear for Murids (including murines and gerbillines) as early as the beginning of the Pliocene (MN14, *ca.* 5.2 Ma), as shown in Tables 2 and 3. All murids show a north–south and east–west diversity gradients (Figure 10; Tables 2 and 3). The category ‘other families’ also follows east–west and north–south gradients. Gerbillines, which have been present in southern Europe since MN12 (*ca.* 4.9–4.0 Ma), are now only present in the southernmost regions but show no significant gradient.

Glirids are also slightly more diversified in the northernmost regions and show a significant latitudinal gradient.

The murine gradient persists during the Late Pliocene (MN15, *ca.* 4.0–3.2 Ma, Table 3). In contrast, arvicolines are now present in all regions and do not show any significant gradient despite the fact that they seem better represented in the northernmost communities than in more southerly communities (Figure 10). The group ‘other families’ is more diversified in northern and eastern regional assemblages (Figure 9), resulting in an east–west gradient (Table 2): sciurids in particular are especially diversified in the northern regions (south Poland) and at the same time absent in the southernmost regions (Figure 8).

Discussion

Biochronologic issues and broad spatiotemporal patterns

As discussed above, evolutionary patterns within communities observed at provincial scale display significant differences. The breaks observed in the different provincial

assemblages are indeed not synchronous. These differences are especially obvious in the Early Miocene and early Late Miocene. South-western provinces rather show a break between biozones MN3 and MN4, whereas more northern and eastern provinces show a break between MN5 and MN6. Likewise, most provinces show a significant break at the beginning of the early Late Miocene (between MN9 and MN10), whereas the Central Iberian province shows a significant break in its assemblage composition earlier between MN7/8 and MN9.

The diverse regional environment types that existed in Europe during the Miocene (Suc et al. 1999; Favre et al. 2007; Jiménez-Moreno and Suc 2007; Costeur and Legendre 2008a) have possibly played a significant role in the diachronous responses of the communities. However, a noticeable faunal endemism has already been noticed by many authors (e.g. Maridet et al. 2007; Casanovas-Vilar et al. 2010; van der Meulen et al. 2011), and especially for Iberian faunas (Gómez Cano et al. 2011). Because of this endemism, the accuracy of the biochronological framework used to correlate mammal bearing localities across Europe has largely been discussed (e.g. Fahlbusch 1991; de Bruijn et al. 1992; Steininger 1999; van Dam 2003; van der Meulen et al. 2011), and uncertainties in the biochronologic system used might also explain part of the diachronic response of the communities (Gómez Cano et al. 2011). Indeed, several authors have pointed out the difficulties to correlate localities (when no magnetostratigraphic or stratigraphic/sedimentologic data can help) due to the diachronous arrival of mammalian taxa usually used as keys to define biochronological units (Abdul Aziz et al. 2008, 2010; Kálin and Kempf 2009; van der Meulen et al. 2011). As recently discussed (van der Meulen et al. 2011), this problem is especially critical for the late Early Miocene due to the fact that many characteristic taxa present delayed arrivals in different regions of Europe, especially in the Iberian peninsula (e.g. *Democricetodon*, *Megacricetodon*, *Eumyarion*, *Cricetodon*, *Keramidomys*, *Eomyops*). Consequently, if diachronic responses of provincial assemblages remain likely because regional environments might develop their own dynamic, it might also be amplified by correlation problems especially between the Iberian fossil record and the rest of Europe. The existence of refuge areas sustaining specific environmental conditions in the northern Iberian Peninsula could also play a significant role in this scheme (Gómez Cano et al. 2011). The same problem is expected for the beginning of the Late Miocene, which is usually recognised in the continental fossil record by the first occurrences of hipparionine and murine mammals. As what happened in the late Early Miocene, some Late Miocene key taxa of Asian origin have been proven to settle progressively from east to west in Europe (Aguilar and Michaux 1996; Agustí et al. 1997; Krijgsman et al. 1994; van Dam et al. 2001). Furthermore, the first murine

rodents are likely relatively rare in the earliest Late Miocene localities (Aguilar and Michaux 1996), implying that their absence in some localities could be simply due to an insufficient sampling effort. Consequently, the attribution of some localities to the latest Middle Miocene or early Late Miocene is questionable, and these uncertainties could also contribute to the delayed response in the composition of the assemblages in some provinces.

Interestingly, the differences observed between our different provincial successions correspond to those periods in which important biochronologic correlation issues have been raised, supporting previous results that some biotic events are noticeably asynchronous across Europe (van der Meulen et al. 2011). However, the same study (van der Meulen et al. 2011) also showed that these diachronous events are also less important than previously suggested, and stated that the MN-biozones remain a useful tool for correlating localities for which no stratigraphic context is available. This biochronologic system has indeed been successfully used many times in other studies covering tens of million year's long records (e.g. Maridet et al. 2007; Eronen et al. 2009; Casanovas-Vilar et al. 2010; Maridet and Costeur 2010). With regard to these conclusions, our results showing the parallel evolution of provincial assemblages and the establishment of diversity gradients linked to environmental and climatic changes confirm that the MN-system remains a reliable tool – although it likely needs an update – when analysing diversity patterns at broad temporal and spatial scale, keeping in mind the limits of the method when comparing occurrences of biotic events.

Temporal versus spatial patterns

The temporal analysis reveals that provincial assemblages seem to be affected by many factors: short climatic events (e.g. at the Oligocene–Miocene boundary), long-term climatic changes (e.g. during the Late Miocene and the Early Pliocene) and also biotic events such as migrations enabled by newly formed land bridges (at the late Early Miocene, Middle Miocene and end of Miocene). As far as spatial patterns are concerned, fewer significant events can be identified. A lengthy interval of regional homogeneity at the European scale is followed by a long period of progressively increasing regional heterogeneity. Initially, from the Late Oligocene to the end of the Middle Miocene, regional communities across Europe are relatively similar in hierarchical composition. The only interruption is a brief interval in the late Early Miocene (MN4, ca. 17.8 Ma), coeval with the massive arrival of Asian-originated taxa after the establishment of the 'Gomphotherium land bridge' (Rögl 1999), during which significant regional differences are evident. Geographical differentiation in the composition of regional assemblages reappears early in the Late Miocene (MN9, ca. 11.1 Ma),

the established gradients are relatively unstable during the Late Miocene, especially during the last period of the Miocene (MN13, *ca.* 6.8–4.9 Ma) when a biogeographic reorganisation seems to occur. Later Murids and ‘other families’ gradients remain stable along the course of the Pliocene.

Considering these trends in the context of paleogeography, it appears that the hierarchical composition of communities was more homogeneous across Europe at the beginning of the studied interval when the landmass was reduced and fragmented by many sea channels, which might seem biogeographically paradoxical. In contrast, the Late Miocene and Pliocene saw significant gradients and periods when particular families were geographically restricted, even though the paleogeography of Europe was growing closer to the extant pattern in which only mountain ranges remain as potential barriers. Furthermore, as shown by the strong similarity of the peri-Mediterranean assemblages, these barriers (such as Pyrenean and Alps mountain ranges) do not play a major role in the differentiation of regional assemblages. Indeed, the rising Pyrenean range does not induce a strong differentiation between the Iberian regional communities’ composition and those from southern France, and it seems that the geographic context has little influence on the differentiation of regional assemblages. However, the climatic context changed dramatically between the late Middle Miocene and Late Miocene, and this factor must also be considered in interpreting paleobiogeographic patterns. The ‘Mid Miocene event’, related to the development of a permanent East Antarctic Ice Sheet, triggered a global climatic change (*ca.* 13.9 Ma, e.g. Flower and Kennett 1994; Zachos et al. 2001; Holbourn et al. 2005; Langebroek et al. 2009; Majewski 2010). This climatic event led to a major change in paleovegetation assemblages, involving the worldwide expansion of low biomass vegetation (e.g. Wolfe 1985; Webb and Opdyke 1995; Cerling et al. 1997; Sun et al. 2012) and the emergence of latitudinally differentiated vegetation due to the strengthening of temperature gradients and seasonality (Wolfe 1985; Bruch et al. 2011). In Europe, the changes were reflected in a general opening of the landscape and a drastic change in vegetation types, culminating in the spread of grasses (Cerling et al. 1997; Suc et al. 1999; Jiménez-Moreno 2006; Favre et al. 2007; Strömberg et al. 2007). In contrast to the overall quite homogeneous vegetation of the Early Miocene (Bruch et al. 2004), distinct regional vegetation types started to appear at this time period (Favre et al. 2007; Jiménez-Moreno et al. 2008). The last typical forest-dominated environments seem to have disappeared at the beginning of the Late Miocene after the Tortonian ‘washhouse climate’ (Böhme et al. 2008), which maintained humid forests in south-western Europe. Even if, in contrast, a trend towards aridity has been proposed in the Iberian Peninsula during the Tortonian (Fortelius et al. 2003; van Dam 2006), the

continuous presence of the still relatively diversified glirid family in the Vallés-Penedés region up to the early Late Miocene rather supports the hypothesis of the ‘washhouse climate’ (Böhme et al. 2008). A dryer climate over continental Europe with fewer regional differences then becomes established, south-western Europe appearing to remain slightly more humid (Böhme et al. 2008). This Late Miocene regional vegetation context broadly persisted through the Messinian period and led to a similar situation in the Early Pliocene (Kovar-Eder et al. 2006; Favre et al. 2007). The overall link observed between spatial diversity patterns and both the vegetation distribution and the underlying climatic context leads to the conclusion that these environmental factors are predominant in explaining the spatial differentiation that appeared among European regional assemblages.

Family-level replacements and adaptive potential

Regional rodent communities react drastically to vegetation and climatic changes, whereas other environmental parameters, such as geography, appear to be less important in explaining the communities’ diversity patterns and renewals at the European scale. In this dynamic, the installation of a diversity gradient appears to be much more related to a glirid–muroid transition rather than to other rodent groups. It is indeed noteworthy that glirids, cricetines, murines and arviculines (rodents that successively dominate the European Neogene along its course) species richness is closely correlated with vegetation or climatic parameters (Daams and van der Meulen 1984; Montuire et al. 1997; Aguilar et al. 1999; Legendre et al. 2005).

Such a link between the diversity of these rodent families and the environmental context can be explained by their ability to fill in a specific type of ecological niche through the adaptation and differential evolution of their life history traits. However, the potential impact of mammal life history traits on their evolution and the structure of their communities is a rather complicated topic as it involves many intermediate scale-bounded mechanisms from the individual to the broad-scale assemblage (Blois and Hadly 2009). Studies based on the European fossil record recently addressed this question by comparing the dynamic of large and small mammals (Liow et al. 2008; Casanovas-Vilar et al. 2010; Maridet and Costeur 2010) but reached different conclusions partly because of different approaches used. Liow et al. (2008) concluded to lower per capita rate of turnovers for small mammals advocating an evolution of a ‘sleep-or-hide’ behaviour (i.e. to adapt to hibernation, torpor and burrowing) in order to accommodate environmental stresses. However, as stated by Casanovas-Vilar et al. (2008), the conclusions of Liow et al. (2008) are partly biased by the fact that they assume the same evolutionary ability for all European

Neogene small mammals, whereas not all extant small mammals possess this ability, depending on their living environment (Gummer 2005). This observation is indeed a rather crucial point since Neogene climate is marked by significant changes that likely induce differentiated responses of small mammals (Maridet and Costeur 2010). Furthermore, among the families that have diversified from the Late Miocene onward and through the glaciations' cycles, only a minority does possess today the ability to hibernate. Consequently, if on one hand it is likely that the adaptation to hibernation *sensu lato* has influenced the evolution of those groups, this ability is on the other hand cannot explain the diversification of other rodent groups. Some other life history traits such as population density-dependent traits or generation rates have been mentioned (van Dam 1997; van Dam and Weltje 1999) but remain difficult to further investigate in the fossil record. All these previously proposed hypotheses emphasise, however, the likely importance of family-level history traits in rodent communities' evolution facing environmental and climatic changes.

Our analysis of the evolutionary history of rodents and of the family-level composition of extant European communities makes it obvious that muroids (especially cricetids and murids) have experienced a real 'success story' throughout the Neogene. Their success, as opposed to the decline of glirids, can be explained by opposite reactions to the general changes in the flora of Europe and more broadly in global climate. All rodent families (and subfamilies) known in the Neogene of Europe are primary plant consumers, and they react differently to these environmental changes, suggesting very different feeding strategies as already indicated by their cheek teeth morphology. The general glirid–muroid transition coevals these environmental changes and the general diversification of vegetation from the Middle Miocene onward, suggesting that a differentiation of their life history traits linked to the consumption of food could be a determinant factor. The previously proposed hypothesis involving rodents' life history traits in their evolutionary dynamic, although they might be true, did not take into account this environmental aspect, thus calling for complementary hypotheses concerning the early differential evolution of life history traits among rodents.

As a matter of fact, digestive tract features and dietary habits known in extant rodents may give interesting insights into how muroids and glirids responded to this transition. The ability of cricetid and murid rodents to feed on various kinds of vegetation (high- and/or low-quality plants depending on species; Langer 2002), thanks to a differentiation of the gastrointestinal tract and especially set-off differentiated sections of the stomach, may explain their rapid diversification and their success in colonising new environments as a reaction to environmental changes. As opposed to this, glirids show an

undifferentiated digestive tract adapted to the digestion of high-quality food (Langer 2002) that is likely to restrict their ability to disperse under changing environmental context. The idea that a 'trade-off between dispersal ability and ecological specialization to local conditions, effective at a metacommunity level, is an important driver of large-scale diversity patterns' has indeed recently been proposed (Jocque et al. 2010). Other ecological characteristics, such as reproductive strategy (reproduction rate, weaning period and litter size), are also strongly linked to digestive tracts structure and dietary habits (Langer 2003) and to environmental conditions (see Bronson 1985 for a review). For instance, compared to cricetids and murids, extant glirids have generally lower reproduction rates and smaller litter sizes (Nowak 1999), suggesting an overall different life history-based adaptive strategy at family level.

Variations in the way family-level diversity reacts can also be observed within Muroidea. Soon after their arrival in Europe, murine rodents induce a renewal among muroids and a new reorganisation within the regional assemblages. Because cricetine diversity starts to decrease at the same time, and because the murine pattern of tooth morphology is supposedly derived from that of cricetines (Jacobs 1977), murines seem to replace cricetines. However, even if less diversified, cricetines coexist with murines in all regional assemblages at the beginning of the Late Miocene. Therefore, we can postulate that they probably occupied different ecological niches. Also, as already proposed by Lindsay and Downs (1998), the decline of cricetines later on does not necessarily imply direct competition with murines. The diversity of cricetine rodents can be directly linked to some local climatic parameters such as mean annual temperatures (MATs). Indeed, a strong relationship links the diversity of their closest extant relative (Legendre et al. 2005) to MATs, whereas it seems totally independent of other factors such as precipitations (Legendre et al. 2005). In contrast, the appearance of murines in Europe can be directly linked to the expansion of open landscapes (Michaux et al. 1997) and to the development of grass-based vegetation in Eurasia from the early Late Miocene onward (Suc et al. 1999; Strömberg et al. 2007). Furthermore, as opposed to cricetines, the relationship established between the murines species richness and the local annual precipitation (Aguilar et al. 1999) comforts the hypothesis that both subfamilies occupied different ecological niches. This suggests that murines may have adapted to different ecological roles within communities even before the early Late Miocene, and that the decline in the diversity of cricetines might simply reflect reduction of their ecological niches during the early Late Miocene. The evolution of regional assemblages from the Late Miocene onward lends credence to this assumption. Indeed, the distribution of their diversity leads to the establishment of a diversity gradient (MN11: *ca.* 8.8–7.8 Ma; Tables 2 and 3),

whereas cricetine diversity decreases more homogeneously in all the regions through the Late Miocene and the Pliocene. A diversity gradient exists not only for murines, but also during the Pliocene for arvicolines. However, the arvicolines are more diversified in northern regions, in contrast to murines (which are more diversified in southern regions). Gerbillines present a much more restricted distribution in time and space, likely related to the distribution of arid conditions. Consequently, as suggested by their differentiated spatial patterns, the overall success of muroid rodents confirms that the involved processes act above generic and species levels where shared life history traits and evolutionary history induce a familial/subfamilial response to climatic changes (Blois and Hadly 2009). An ability of muroids to rapidly evolve their family-/subfamily-level life history traits while facing environmental changes would in turn explain the ‘success story’ of European cricetids and murids facing climatic changes since the Middle Miocene, whereas other rodent families faded at the same time. This conclusion also speaks in favour of taking into consideration higher taxon ecological features in rodent diversity conservation issues facing environmental changes, in accordance with observations made by Amori and Gippoliti (2001, 2003).

Supplementary information

Supplementary material can be viewed online, it includes:

- Text S1: list of fossil localities and bibliographic references used to build the data-set.
- Table S1: data matrix of presence/absence of fossil rodent species by region and biochronological unit.
- Table S2: taxonomic richness for each region and biochronological unit.

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